

CHINESE NATIONAL ACADEMIC SINGING AS A PHENOMENON OF THE CONTEMPORARY MUSIC ART

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Abstract

Academic art in the new century is increasingly gaining new followers: performers, composers, and listeners, and new forms of embodiment along with traditional ones. It reveals at concerts, festivals, competitions, and is heard in music programs around the world. It never ceases to interest scientists who try on new approaches, methods of analysis and research. This all creates a necessity to clarify the concepts and characteristics of different developments, and to expand the empirical field of study including a variety of experiences from the West, East, and China. One of the new phenomena in the Chinese vocal art has become a synthesis of national tradition and European bel canto. This article is dedicated to this phenomenon. The term itself, its definition and cultural meaning is discussed here. We suggest a new term of “Chinese national academic art”, define its developing sound ideal which is given in comparison with other types of singing common in China – the folk singing and the European bel canto. The conclusion of our study is clear: in the formation of a new type of singing in China, two trends simultaneously prevail – on the one hand, the use of European bel canto techniques, on the other, the desire to preserve the national sound ideal.

Keywords: Chinese national academic singing, types of singing in China, folk singing, European academic tradition, bel canto.

There are different types of singing present in the contemporary musical art in China. One can single out at least three main ones that are considered as a part of tradition in the national culture: the traditional Chinese folk singing, the European bel canto singing and a new type emerging as a result of an integration between the two aforementioned. The last type is still young and in the stage of development, so it doesn't have a commonly-accepted name yet, is not clearly defined (has no specified denotation) and is not associated with a specified meaning (its own features). This type of singing doesn't even have its own genres which would be characteristic to it only. It influences all the kinds and genres of music changing their techniques and creative output, which is easy to explain: academization as a reason for metamorphoses in art appears firstly in the minds of creators and consumers, reflects in their artistic endeavors, creates a sound ideal¹ and so cannot be limited by any one part of the art. The most important notion is that especially interesting the problem of development of a new singing style in China is made by its deep foundation, its national roots.

This problem attracts the attention of Chinese musicologists, which is a reason for writing this article. As a material for consideration we use the ideas of such Chinese researchers as “Li Shen” (1986), “Qiao Xinjian” (1990), “Zhou Xiaoyan” (1992), “Duan Youfang” (2006), “Liu Dong” (2007), “Xing Lu” (2007), “Yang Changjian” (2010), “Zhang Wenwen” (2012), “Wu Yan” (2016), “Zhao Ling” (2020), “Li Shanshan” (2021) that were presented in their articles of the last 40 years. These authors pose specific questions connected

to the comprehension of musical phenomena and earlier periods of the Chinese history and search for their place in the national culture.

A separate question is if we should single out this new type of singing as a specific thing or include it in the general term of folk singing. Chinese researchers have different opinions.

Such musicologists as aforementioned “Zhou Xiaoyan” (1992), “Yang Changjian” (2010), “Yang Changjian” (2010), “Li Shanshan” (2021) include national academic singing into the folk singing. Others such as “Qiao Xinjian” (1990), “Liu Dong” (2007), “Zhao Ling” (2020) consider it as a separate type. “Li Sheng” (1986) who wrote about this problem earlier than others suggested that the Chinese singing as a type allows to “unite” the national academic singing and the folk singing (Li Sheng 1986: 23).

Since the national academic singing is a new type created by the integration of the folk singing and the bel canto, as it was specified by “Liu Dong” (2007: 34), one cannot fully accept it neither as a type belonging to the bel canto nor a kind of the folk singing. It is not hard to notice that all the researchers who use for this type new terms such as “new folk singing”, “modern folk singing”, “academic singing of a Chinese kind”, etc. have already established it as a specific type.

As is already said, most frequently used words for this “integrated singing type” as we defined it in the beginning of the article are “national”, “Chinese”, “new”. The recent addition is “the academic singing of a Chinese kind”.

¹ By the sound ideal we mean what B.V. Asafiev called “hearing of a nation”, a specific national understanding of beauty in the art. Every culture has its own examples treated by the ethno-social group as an ideal: for the Russian folk instrumental music such exemplars are the harmonica

timbres; for the Polish culture it is a small rih that created the phenomenon of “bound violin”; for the Chinese singings these are first of all high register voices (both male and female) etc.

Let us shortly introduce the names used to describe this type of singing that are presented in the scientific studies. Some researchers such as “Li Shanshan” (2021), “Wu Yan” (2016), “Yang Changjian” (2010) use in their articles a common term “folk singing” (民族唱法). However, the authors see problems with it. “Li Sheng” (1986: 23) concluded already in the 1980s that “folk singing” should be renamed as “Chinese singing” because the words “folk” or “national” applied to it seem ambiguous since China has a lot of ethnical groups with their own methods of singing, He considered the best term for both the new type of singing and the folk singing to be “Chinese singing” (中国唱法).

Other researchers such as “Duan Youfang” (2006), “Liu Dong” (2007), “Xing Lu” (2007), “Zhang Wenwen” (2012) used a more detailed description: “a new folk singing” or “a modern folk singing” (新民族唱法, 现代民族唱法). As evident, these authors highlighted a quality characteristic of being new or a temporal one of belonging to our days.

Moreover, according to the Qiao Xinjian’s article “Brief discussion of a new type of national singing” the term “national singing” (民族唱法) was already established in the end of the XX century in the everyday speech, and the phrase “new national singing” (新民族唱法; 民族新唱法) was present in the academic discussion (Qiao Xinjian 1990: 103). We can also notice that the author used the most interesting for us term of “new the type of national singing” (民族新唱法) in the title of the work and wrote about it as about a new kind.

In her recent article «Comparison of the method of new folk singing and traditional folk singing - using the example of “Jin Tielin’s method of singing”» a Chinese musicologist Zhao Ling suggested one more name, different from the aforementioned. She thinks that this method of new singing can be called “the academic singing of the Chinese type” (学院派唱法) (Zhao Ling 2020: 61). We see here that the author suggests singling out more specific, narrow type of academic singing considering features bound to the culture (civilization). Zhao Lin obviously understands the European academic singing as a specific type too, and perhaps, not the only one. If the word “Chinese” is understood as a synonym of the “national”, it appears to be the most often used among all the mentioned.

As a result of the analysis of the phenomenon in question and defining its essence we developed our own term and suggest to call it “the national academic singing” as opposed to the European bel canto tradition and meaning a symbiosis of a universal² art movement colored by a national tradition.

Therefore, the Chinese vocal tradition can be divided into three separate types of singing:

1. Folk singing of the Chinese tradition (民族民间唱法 · 传统唱法 · 民歌唱法 · 民族唱法)

2. Bel canto singing of the European tradition (美声唱法, 西洋唱法, 欧洲唱法)

3. National academic singing (学院派民族唱法, 现代民族唱法 · 新民族唱法).

Let us shortly discuss here each of these types.

The folk singing in a broad sense³ includes singing of any kind of ethnic music and any kind of Chinese drama. It is obvious that the Chinese vocal music has a long history: already during the Shang dynasty (1600 – 1046 BC) there were professional singers in China who served the royals and the nobles (Zhou Xiaoyan 1992: 38). Then China stepped into the period of the first centralized state, the Qin dynasty (246–207 BC). The First Qin Emperor was a great reformer of the governance, standardization, education: he regulated the system of weights and measures, unified hieroglyphics, implemented the strict bureaucratic system. In the central part of the Qin Empire a musical center of different ethnical groups formed with Han being the main one (Zhou Xiaoyan 1992: 38). The Qin Empire was a part of the Han period (III BC – III AD) which was the time of the highest political advancement of the Ancient China. The Han ethnos established itself as the most cultured and evolved.

After a long time of barbarian invasions leading to the decentralization, the Empire was united again in the second half of the first millennium AD by the Sui and Tang dynasties. (581–907). The emperor’s court established schools specializing in the musical mastery including vocal (Zhou Xiaoyan 1992: 38). Later, under the Ming and Qing dynasties (1368–1911), musical-theatrical genres emerged and developed throughout China – Chinese dramas (Zhou Xiaoyan 1992: 38), the most significant of which is Beijing opera⁴. Together with this musical genre a specific type (technique) of singing emerged that later will be considered as a part of folk singing,

Besides singing in dramas, as we mentioned before, Chinese folk singing still includes singing song of the Han ethnos because the Han ethnic group plays the leading role in the life of China. Han folk songs can be divided into three big kinds (Zhou Qingqing 2010: 13–19): Haozi (号子) are sung during labor; 2) Shan’ge literally means “a song in the mountains” and is characterized by the high loud singing and free rhythm; Xiaodiao (小调) is singing at leisure. It is thematically closer to the city than the village life, its rhythm is stricter, and there is a specific composition for a song, a beautiful melody and a gentle, fine text. Its performers are not only commoners but professional singer as well. As a result, Xiadiao has a higher degree of complexity. Mainly, the distinction between these kinds is that Haozi is sung during labor and its melodies are simple and rhythmical, singing demands a strong voice. Shange is sung by a high-pitched voice, Xiaodiao is more melodic. These characteristics are important to

² Universality is the most important feature of the academic art

³ In a narrow sense, Chinese folk singing is performing songs of the earliest and most numerous han ethnos and traditional

Chinese dramas. Usually we use the term in this narrow sense.

⁴ Besides Beijing opera, Kunqu, Nuo opera, Ping opera, Henan opera and other were popular

consider when we discuss some ideas connected to singing,

The second type of singing we have mentioned is *bel canto*. According to the Merriam-Webster, “*bel canto*: operatic singing originating in 17th century and 18th century Italy and stressing ease, purity, and evenness of tone production and an agile and precise vocal technique” [1].

Bel canto is known in China since the middle of the XIX century. It is understood not as a vocal technique only, but as the European musical tradition in its whole. After the First Opium war (1840) this system was brought by the Europeans to China; simultaneously, the Chinese studied it abroad. In the first third of the XX century, Chinese “musical pioneers” founded in their country musical schools imitating the European system, the most well known of them is the State Special Musical Institute (国立音乐专科学校) which became the Shanghai conservatory today. With regard to *bel canto* in that period, in Shanghai its development was connected with the name of a Russian bass V.G. Shushlin (苏石林 Sū Shílín). Vladimir Shushlin (26.07.1896–23.10.1978) worked in Shanghai for more than 25 years. A prominent Chinese composer, rector of the Shanghai conservatory since 1950s He Liuting called Shushlin the founder of the Chinese *bel canto* (Wu Chao 2015: 5).

New musical establishments not only cultivated European music, but from the start also combined European musical systems creatively with the traditional Chinese music and taught both, so Chinese students learnt both type of singing simultaneously.

By creatively merging the European musical tradition with the Chinese traditional music, “musical pioneers” created musical academic institutions for learning Chinese traditional music. The most well known was the Lu Xun Yanan Art Institute, opened in 1938 (Yan'An Lu Xun Institute of Arts: Red Memory). There in 1945 the first Chinese opera “The White-Haired Girl” (白毛女 Bái máo nǚ) by Ma Ke (马可 Mǎ kě) and others was created (Wu Chao 2015: 12–13).

After establishing of the People's Republic of China in 1949, the violent confrontation of ideas occurred in the Chinese musical society concerning the relationship between China and the West in the area of music. It is known as “the fight between the imported and the local” (土洋之争 tǔyáng zhī zhēng) (Zhang Wenwen 2012: 270–271). Concerning singing, the question was what was better, the *bel canto* or the folk singing. *Bel canto* apologists said the folk singing was not scientific, technically unhealthy for singers, with a shrill and unpleasant sound. The folk singing defenders found *bel canto* to be unemotional, obscure, and so not able to find its way to the mass audience. The end result of this discussion was the understanding that these two singing methods should not be opposed but combined and complement each other. We can name many folk singers now (Wan Kun, Go Lanying, etc.) who try to implement *bel canto* techniques into folk singing, perform Chinese songs and drama and achieve some success, according to the “Liu Dong's” article (2007: 34).

Let us remind that with the cultural revolution of 1966 all kinds of art and the Chinese culture itself were

in decline and severely damaged. In that period, the folk singing was declared untouchable from the political reasons and prevailed. After the end of the Cultural revolution (1976) and following reforms, all previously suppressed arts including the *bel canto* singing bloomed again.

Now we will discuss the problem of the national academic singing. In the end of the 1980s – beginning of the 1990s, the symbol of the emerging national academic singing became the development of the vocal school and pedagogical system of the professor Jin Tielin (Liu Dong 2007) who was the rector of the Chinese Conservatory of Music (Beijing) since 1981 and died recently (November 2022).

As we have already said, the Chinese national academic singing is a new type of singing that emerged on base of the traditional Chinese singing (Han songs and drama) and the European *bel canto* tradition. In relation to the singing language, the features of the national singings are the same as of the folk singing, vocals must be clearly pronounced. In the pure academic singing, for creating a unified timbre so called narrow vocals are often used instead of wide vocals (for example, “a” is often sung close to “o” and even “u”). In the Chinese folk singing and national singing both high and low sounds have to differ clearly (“a” as “a”, “i” as “i” etc.).

In relation to breathing, the modern national singing is based on the techniques of the academic singing and supposes the body stretched and the diaphragm opened.

The national singing is based upon the folk singing: its sound is bright, its vibrato is little, the sound can be straight, the resonances is not chased much so the loudness is not big (Li Shanshan 2021: 115). But in the process of singing the national approach demands to open the throat and to rise the palate as well as the academic one.

Given that the Chinese folk singing is based on the head voice and doesn't give much attention to the chest resonance, it is characterized by a quiet and shrill voice (Yang Changjian 2010: 131). Although now perfection of the resonance is given more attention in the national singing, it is still similar to the folk singing with low volume of sound. So national singers need the help of microphones for singing Chinese national operas. It is well seen in an example of “The Ballad of the Canal” (运河谣 Yùnhé yáo) which was premiered in the National center of the performing arts on the 21 June 2012.

The main ideal of the sound in musical art for Chinese people is still a high voice (Ma Zixing 1998: 57). Almost all singers who use folk singing method (performing ancient songs, dramas etc.) have high voices. Even after the European musical system spread widely in China, for a long time operas written in China didn't have parts for medium or low voices. As an example, we can name “The White-Haired girl” by Ma Ke and others, “Sister Zang” by Yang Su and others (Ma Zixing 1998: 57).

This reflects also upon the national academic singing. Students without a high voice are recommended to study the *bel canto*, and only those who with a high voice may study the national academic singing. This

leads to the situation when in the operas written by Chinese composers especially for singers of the national academic singing all the lower parts are performed by bel canto singers which is evident not only in the area of the traditional Chinese vocal art, but also in the area of instrumental music. It is also a feature of modern Chinese folk orchestras to have cellos and double basses of European type for base parts. So two coexisting trends are clearly evident in the process of the development of this new type of singing in China: using European technologies on the one hand and up keeping a national sound ideal on the other.

Let us summarize. As a form of integration of the Chinese folk singing and the European bel canto tradition, the Chinese national academic singing was born more than 40 years ago. It has developed as a specific Chinese type of the academic singing, It has a lot of problems, but it is important to look upon it from a dialectical point of view: if following generations will constantly work on it, the Chinese national singing will develop through the transformation of quantity into quality and will become a vocal art with its own proper place in the national and world vocal culture.

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